

Scenario 01

A software development team is at sprint zero of an innovation project. The project has the following technical restrictions defined by the client: user data must be encrypted in the registration, requests during operations cannot take more than 500 ms, the application must work on IOS and Android, and finally, the application must connect with credit platforms in real-time. The technical leader discusses the technologies to be used and marks with TRUE the corresponding leaf nodes in the Bayesian network: Keystore, Auth, Electron, Web Services, GRPC, and Retrofit. At the end of the analysis, the technical leader runs the network and visualizes each intermediate node's calculated probabilities. Some nodes showed a high probability, representing the network's semantics that they are potential risks: security flaw in persistence and lack of scalability in the data. With this information, the team evaluated the technologies' choice, marking new technologies on the network and replacing some of the initially chosen ones. One possibility analyzed is to exchange Electron technology for Ionic. After this change in the network, the intermediate nodes' probabilities that represent the risks mentioned above have significantly decreased. The technical leader, together with the team, will evaluate the change of this technology to execute the project.

Scenario 02

A software development team is at sprint zero of an innovation project. The client's project restrictions: the application must support the users' high media load processing; the user can apply filters to the images and view the processing in less than one second; user groups interactive chat. Finally, the application must work on IOS and Android. The technical leader evaluates the technologies to be used to achieve the objectives with the lowest possible risk. The technological leader discusses the technologies to be used with the team and marks TRUE the corresponding leaf nodes of these technologies in the Bayesian network: Ionic, Glide, Room, and Couchdb library. At the end of the analysis, the technical leader runs the network and visualizes each intermediate node's calculated probabilities. Nodes showed a high probability, representing the network's semantics that they are potential risks: error in the asynchronous display of images and low performance in the media's display. With this information, the team evaluated the technologies' choice, marking new technologies on the network and replacing some of the initially chosen ones. One possibility analyzed is to exchange the Glide technology for Picasso and add the Kotlin coroutines technology. After these changes in the network, the intermediate nodes' probabilities that represent the risks mentioned above have significantly decreased. Together with the team, the technical leader will evaluate the change of this technology to execute the project.

Scenario 03

A software development team is at sprint zero of an innovation project. The project has the following technical restrictions defined by the client: the application must communicate in real-time with different legacy systems of the client via web services, the communication must be asynchronous, the user's Google account can carry out authentication. Finally, the

application should work on IOS and Android. The technical leader evaluates the technologies to be used to achieve the objectives with the lowest possible risk. The technological leader discusses the technologies to be used with the team and marks with TRUE the corresponding leaf nodes of these technologies in the Bayesian network: Firebase, Apollo library, REST, Ionic, and RxJava. At the end of the analysis, the technical leader runs the network and visualizes each intermediate node's calculated probabilities. Some nodes had a high probability, representing in the network semantics, that they are potential risks: failure with hotspots via a third-party application and loss of configuration in the build-tools versioning. With this information, the team evaluated the technologies' choice, marking new technologies on the network and replacing some of the initially chosen ones. One possibility analyzed is to exchange the RxJava technology for Rxswift. After this change in the network, the intermediate nodes' probabilities that represent the risks mentioned above have decreased significantly. Together with the team, the technical leader will evaluate the change of this technology to execute the project.

Scenario 04

A project is under development by a team that uses the Scrum methodology. Currently, the team reported that the project faces a technological risk: loss of configuration when accessing microservices using Firebase authentication. This information corresponds to an intermediate node in the network. The main technologies used in the development are NodeJs using Firebase, Apollo library to consume services, and JWT framework for data security. The technical leader marked this information as TRUE in the Bayesian Network, executed the network, and calculated the nodes' probabilities. The technical leader observed the node's probability corresponding to the risk and evaluate options in the network, marking as TRUE some nodes representing mitigation strategies. When choosing nodes: reviewing the dependencies in build gradle and evaluating proxy settings, the risk mentioned above has significantly decreased probability. The team will assess the recommendations to define the project's risk mitigation strategies.

Scenario 05

A project is under development by a team that uses the Scrum methodology. Currently, the team informed that the project has a technological risk: loss of connection of the application in HTTP request via Postman. This information corresponds to an intermediate node in the network. The main technologies used in the development are Ionic for hybrid development, the retrofit library for making requests, and the Push Notifications service from Google. The technical leader marked this information as TRUE in the Bayesian Network, executed the network, and calculated nodes' probabilities. The technological leader observed the node's probability corresponding to the risk and evaluate options in the network, marking as TRUE some nodes representing mitigation strategies. The risk mentioned above decreased significantly when choosing the node: inserting the Authorization header in the Retrofit settings. The team will evaluate the recommendation to define the project's risk mitigation strategies.

Scenario 06

A project is under development by a team that uses the Scrum methodology. Currently, the team reported that the project faces a technological risk: loss of data in a hybrid server database. This information corresponds to an intermediate node in the network. The main technologies used in the development are Ionic for hybrid development, REST services, Mongoose to access the bank, and Firebase for authentication. The technical leader marked this information as TRUE in the Bayesian Network, executed the network, and calculated the nodes' probabilities. The technological leader observed the node's probability corresponding to the risk and evaluate options in the network, marking as TRUE some nodes representing mitigation strategies. When choosing nodes: exporting the instance of the bank's scheme and updating the Ionic version, the risk mentioned above decreased significantly. The team will evaluate the recommendations to define the project's risk mitigation strategies.